

**“HEALTH ORIENTED ENVIRONMENT IN A GENERAL
EDUCATION ESTABLISHMENT” SPECIAL COURSE FOR
“HUMAN HEALTH” SPECIALTY STUDENTS**

O. M. Bellorin-Herrera, O. V. Kavatska

V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University (Kharkiv, Ukraine)

E-mail: bellher@ukr.net, kabatsckaya.margo@yandex.ru

**СПЕЦКУРС «ЗДОРОВ'ЯОРІЄНТОВАНЕ СЕРЕДОВИЩЕ
ЗАГАЛЬНООСВІТНЬОГО НАВЧАЛЬНОГО ЗАКЛАДУ»
ДЛЯ СТУДЕНТІВ СПЕЦІАЛЬНОСТІ «ЗДОРОВ'Я ЛЮДИНИ»**

О. М. Бельорін-Еррера, О. В. Кабацька

*Харківський національний університет імені В. Н. Каразіна
(м. Харків, Україна)*

The article analyses the present day state of the problem of the pedagogical staff readiness for health-oriented school environment creation. On the results of the pilot research on the readiness of both working and future health basics teachers for health oriented school environment creation a number of problems in the methodological training of the staff has been revealed. Grounding on the results of the experiment results and scientific and methodological literature analysis the “Health Oriented Environment in a General Education Establishment” special course program has been developed. The special course program comprehension will facilitate future health basics teachers to master efficient methods of health oriented school environment creation, which will promote, in the result, their integral professional readiness for provision of the functioning of the environment in a general educational establishment

oriented on preservation and improvement of health of all educational process participants

Key words: methodological preparation, future health basics teacher, health oriented school environment, special course.

Introduction. It is known that educational efficiency mainly depends on the state of health of students and teachers. Unfortunately, the modern statistics reports the progressing decline of health of educational age subjects. As the researches show, many factors, which perform ill influence on the health, are connected with educational environment [9, p.21].

Educational environment defines the character of human behaviour pattern, forms their needs and customs for all the life. That is why it is necessary to design the educational process in such a way that not only the subject knowledge acquiring will become a priority, but the development of the creative potential, health culture formation, healthy lifestyle motivation, creation of educational environment, oriented on preserving and strengthening of all health component parts of educational process subjects.

In our opinion, the leading condition for successful solving of the health oriented environment creation in a general education establishment is the professional competence of a teacher. The teacher, first of all the health basics teacher as health culture bearer, educates responsible attitude towards personal health and the health of surrounding people in the child, as the head of school valeological service takes care about the health of all educational process subjects. Thus, a teacher who has undergone special training for health oriented school environment creation can do for the health of schoolchildren, teachers, and school authority members even much more than a medical service representative.

Topicality. In accordance with actuality and acuteness of the given problem in the last years there has been spread a tendency of scientific consideration of training issues of students — future teachers — to creating, in general educational establishments, an educational environment, oriented on preservation and improvement of health of subjects of education. There have appeared scientific publications [7; 10] and monographs [1; 3] on this subject matter, though, complex researches of methodical training of future health basics teachers as for creation health oriented school environment have been absent in Ukraine as well as abroad.

The layout of the main material. Considering the importance of solving this problem, the Department of Valeology of V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National

University has performed a pilot research project, which highlights the present day state of training future health basics teachers for creation health oriented school environment.

The research intended to perform a questionnaire poll, questioning and talks among students, professors of higher educational establishments, teachers and administration staff of general education schools of Ukraine.

The results of talks, questionings and forms processing show that nowadays there has appeared a necessity of training improvement of future health basics teachers for creating health oriented school environment. So, for instance, 75 % of the questioned students of the Department of Valeology of V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University have expressed the need for intensification the knowledge as for creating health oriented school environment.

The questioning among practicing teachers and methodologists of general education schools, including those where students of the Department of Valeology of V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University underwent internship practice, and also professors of higher educational establishments, proved topicality of future health basics teachers' training for creating a health oriented school environment, allowed to define key issues of its content and development of the relevant educational and methodical provision.

Thereby, relying upon the received results of the pilot research, and also supporting the idea that "professional training of future specialists in human health requires search and application of new methods, means, educational forms, new organization of educational process" [5], for the purpose of effective assistance for students in understanding the knowledge and skills as for creating health oriented school environment at the Department of Valeology of V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University there was devised a general education special course "Health Oriented Environment of a General Education Establishment", which is due to become a central link of methodical training of future health basics teachers for creating health oriented school environment.

To study the special course "Health Oriented Environment of a General Education Establishment" 1.5 ECTS credits are allocated.

The special course "Health Oriented Environment of a General Education Establishment" is to consolidate, deepen, unite and structure the previously studied knowledge by student on the following subjects: "General Valeology", "Physical Health Basics", "Healthy Lifestyle Physiology", "Psychophysiological Basics of Health", "Concepts of Valeological Outlook", "Ecological

Valeology”, “Moral and Spiritual Foundations of Health”, “Valeological Culture of Nutrition”, “Principles of Personal and Social Safety”, “Philosophy”, “Pedagogics”, and also to support formation and better understanding of new notions for a student, help future health basics teachers to find the best methods of solving problems as for creating health oriented school environment, that, in the result, will allow to form an integral professional readiness for creating health oriented school environment.

The special course “Health Oriented Environment of a General Education Establishment” consists of two content modules. The first of which — “The Conception of Health Oriented Educational Environment in Historical-Pedagogical and Valeological aspects — aimed at 1) formation in students a theoretical basis of the named environment creation; 2) consideration of such notions as “person and environment”, “educational environment”, “health oriented school environment” and 3) the outline of the teacher’s role in its formation and preservation. In the process of the special course studies future teachers are introduced to structural components, main performance, quantitative parameters and the principles of health oriented school environment organization.

In our opinion, for the arousing of interest and motivation of students to deepen their knowledge as for creating a health oriented environment of a general education establishment the main role belongs to the introductory lecture, as it is exactly this lecture which prepares a student for this course understanding. The introductory lecture “Health Oriented Environment of a General Education Establishment” is designed in such a way that to provide students with integral understanding of this sphere of their pedagogical activity, to emphasis topicality, practical importance, aim, to give details of the course tasks, to give information about information sources, terms and forms of reporting.

For optimal combination of lectures with systematic individual scientific-educational activity of students, development of creative thinking among future specialists, ability to apply theoretical knowledge to solve practical tasks, engagement of future health basics teachers to a scientific research as for creation a health oriented school environment, provision of system revision, intensification and consolidation of knowledge on creating a health oriented school environment, the special course program envisages the conduct of seminar lessons. This type of practical classes foresees individual study of certain topics and problems concerning the creation of a health oriented school

environment by students, discussion of individual work results, represented in the form of theses, reports, talks, essays, project presentations. So, for instance, one of seminar lessons, during which students perform a comparative analysis of opinions of prominent philosophers, teachers, and psychologists of the past — J. A. Komensky, J.-J. Rousseau, J. H. Pestalozzi, P. F. Lesgaft, J. Korczak, A. S. Makarenko, J. Gibson, V. O. Sukhomlynsky — on the idea of education, the principles of upbringing and their connection with the health state of a child, is held in the form of a seminar-discussion. The chosen format accustoms future health basics teachers to independent thinking, promotes the development of their analytical skills, abilities to prove personal opinion, thoughtful argumentation, respect of the opponent's opinion.

Lecture classes, devoted to the detailed familiarization of future health basics teachers with the state of the problem development of the problem of health preservation and improvement of schoolchildren in an educational environment of general education establishments of Ukraine [2; 8], Russia [4], and also with approaches to the creation of favourable school environment in the most developed countries of the world (Sweden [15], Finland [14], the United States of America [12; 13; 16]), there are held as scientific-practical lessons in the form of lectures-conferences with problems set beforehand and the system of talks of 5–10 minutes long. The combination of the presented talks allows highlighting the problem of health improvement in the educational environment of domestic and foreign general education establishments from many sides. At the end of such lecture the teacher summarizes the talks of the students, complementing or specifying the presented information, helps students to formulate conclusions.

To consolidate and visualize the received information the program of this module provides an excursion to the Health promoting school, in terms of which students attend sport venues, socialize with school children and their parents, get acquainted with the work of the school canteen, medical room, valeological service, have an opportunity to assess hygienic conditions, get acquainted with the organization of outer school work and ask questions to teachers-practitioners and representative of the school administration.

And, finally, on the basis of synthesis of the previous personal research, the future teachers formulate their understanding of health oriented school environment, as they imagine. The lessons are held in the “round table” format. The structure of the argumentative, demonstrative talks which students produce to the wider audience consideration, promotes formation of creative thinking

among the future health basics teachers, which is extremely necessary for a modern highly-qualified specialist, oriented on the work under conditions of high professional competition.

The content of theoretical and practical knowledge, which compose the second module — “The conditions of health oriented general education establishment environment creation”, – allows equipping of students – the future health basics teachers – with practical knowledge to analyze normative documentation as for the condition of the school environment, assess the correspondence of the school environment to hygiene and sanitary norms and standards, compose the algorithm of health oriented school environment project, design models of health oriented school environment, test health oriented school environment, perform growth monitoring of health oriented school environment.

Regarding complexity and rather large volume of the material provided by the module program, along with topic lectures, aimed for consequent, system layout of its content, there are conducted lectures with the help of technical means of education and audio-video equipment, which are to provide visualization of the lecture material with the idea of facilitating its comprehension and successful fulfillment of exercises by students at practical lessons on the lecture material. For instance, a lecture lesson, devoted to consideration of the methods of vector modeling of the society, suggested by V. Jasvin, on the background of the analysis of the “educational environment” typology by J. Korczak, [11, p. 31–45], for its better comprehension it is supplemented with demonstration of visual materials (schemes, tables, graphs) in the form of slides. After this, at practical lessons, students under the teacher’s guidance consolidate theoretical provisions and acquire abilities and skills of their practical application, while working at the construction of the vector, responsible for different types of educational environment in the coordinate system, which consists of two axes: “freedom-dependence” and “activity-passivity”.

Binary lectures in the form of a dialogue of a scientist and a practitioner are provided while considering normative documentation concerning school environment and assessing correspondence of the school environment to hygiene and sanitary norms and standards. The teacher gives lessons in the form of a dialogue with representatives of school administration in the first case, and with representatives of State Sanitary and Epidemiological Service in the other.

Seminar lessons, provided by the second module program, except developing and educational functions, also perform the function of

comprehension control of the educational material as for creating health oriented school environment and reveal gaps in their knowledge and abilities. So, to logically complete the special course study there is a performance of personal project work by a student of a health oriented school environment and its presentation. The presentation has to demonstrate strong and weak sides in the knowledge comprehension by students, which allows a teacher an opportunity to analyze and assess the level of student's readiness for a health oriented school environment creation.

Nevertheless, a lot of mistakes can be avoided at the beginning of the project elaboration, having used the individual consultation of a teacher. Individual consultation, in our opinion, facilitates the better comprehension of the new notions for the student, helps future specialists to gain information about additional literature sources, and also to find better methods for the set problems solution.

Consultations can also be group ones. At the end of the studies of the "Health Oriented Environment in a General Education Establishment" special course there is a planned lecture-consultation, which is held in accordance with the "questions-answers" principle. The teacher, during the time of the lecture answers students' questions, which appeared during the process of the acquiring knowledge on the course. In the meantime, a lecture-consultation solves problems of the preparation of students for writing a credit test paper on the whole special course program.

The recommended literature [1; 3; 6; 11] for the special course "Health Oriented Environment in a General Education Establishment" reflects the main ideas of the special course, promotes the better understanding and comprehension of the lecture material, helps students in the practical tasks performance, becomes of use while preparing for talks at seminars and own health oriented school environment project development.

The assessment of educational achievements of students on the results of teaching the "Health Oriented Environment in a General Education Establishment" special course is performed, on the assumption of the division of the maximum available score of 100 for separate types of educational activity, namely: for the work at practical and seminar lessons — 20 points at most, for individual work — 20 points at most, for developing and defending the health oriented school environment project — 30 points at most, for final test on the content module — 30 points at most.

Conclusion. While studying the present day state problem of future teachers training for health oriented school environment creation, we have concluded that presently there have been formed certain notions about concept backgrounds of such work and its main directions, there have been achieved encouraging results on certain aspects of health oriented activity in the conditions of educational establishments. At the same time, there has become apparent that it is not sufficient for transformation of an ordinary general education school into a school of health oriented incline to perform a simple number of separate preventive, health improving and correctional measures, application of health improving technologies. It requires a system, complex approach towards creating certain favourable conditions for educational and teaching activity of a general education school on the basis of partnership of competent teachers, medics, valeologists, competent administrative staff, schoolchildren, parents and the public, which will provide a possibility to create a health oriented school environment, where factors of the educational process harmful for health will be maximally reduced or completely eliminated.

To solve this problem, at the Department of Valeology of V. N. Karazin National University there has been started a methodical training of future health basics teachers, the central component of which is the “Health Oriented Environment in a General Education Establishment” special course, aimed on solving a number of questions as for future teachers’ preparation, which were found during the conduct of the pilot research. The result of the preparation must become the readiness of future health basics teachers for health oriented school environment creation.

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**Бельорін-Еррера О. М., Кабацька О. В. Спецкурс
«Здоров'яорієнтоване середовище загальноосвітнього навчального
закладу» для студентів спеціальності «Здоров'я людини»**

У статті проаналізовано сучасний стан проблеми готовності педагогічних кадрів до створення здоров'яорієнтованого шкільного середовища. За підсумками пілотажного дослідження готовності працюючих та майбутніх учителів основ здоров'я до створення здоров'яорієнтованого шкільного середовища виявлено низку проблем щодо методичної підготовки педагогічних кадрів до цієї роботи. На підставі результатів експерименту та аналізу науково-методичної літератури розроблено програму спецкурсу «Здоров'яорієнтоване середовище загальноосвітнього навчального закладу». Засвоєння програми спецкурсу допоможе майбутнім учителям основ здоров'я опанувати ефективні методи створення здоров'яорієнтованого шкільного середовища, що в підсумку сприятиме формуванню в них цілісної професійної готовності до забезпечення функціонування в загальноосвітньому навчальному закладі шкільного середовища, орієнтованого на збереження та зміцнення здоров'я всіх учасників освітнього процесу.

Ключові слова: методична підготовка, майбутній учитель основ здоров'я, здоров'яорієнтоване шкільне середовище, спецкурс.

**Бельорин-Эррера А. М., Кабацкая Е. В. Спецкурс
«Здоровьеориентированная среда общеобразовательного учебного заведения» для студентов специальности «Здоровье человека»**

В статье проанализировано современное состояние проблемы готовности педагогических кадров к созданию здоровьесориентированной школьной среды. По итогам пилотажного исследования готовности работающих и будущих учителей основ здоровья к созданию здоровьесориентированной школьной среды выявлен ряд проблем в методической подготовке педагогических кадров к этой работе. На основании результатов эксперимента и анализа научно-методической литературы разработана программа спецкурса «Здоровьесориентированная среда общеобразовательного учебного заведения». Усвоение программы спецкурса поможет будущим учителям основ здоровья освоить эффективные методы создания здоровьесориентированной школьной среды, что в итоге будет способствовать формированию у них целостной профессиональной готовности к обеспечению функционирования в общеобразовательном учебном заведении школьной среды, ориентированной на сохранение и укрепление здоровья всех участников образовательного процесса.

Ключевые слова: методическая подготовка, будущий учитель основ здоровья, здоровьесориентированная школьная среда, спецкурс.

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